

Effect of Brassica nigra seeds

extract against hepatocellular proliferation induced by phenobarbital as tumor promoter agent

Efecto del extracto de semillas de Brassica nigra contra la proliferación hepatocelular inducida por fenobarbital como agente promotor de tumores

Ibtehal Naseer Salman, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology/ College of Pharmacy/ Mustansiriya University, Baghdad, Iraq, dr.bahirrazzaq@uomustansiriya.edu.iq, orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4421-8690> Email: ph.ibtehal@gmail.com

Bahir Abdul-Razzaq Mshimesh*, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology/ College of Pharmacy/ Mustansiriya University, Baghdad, Iraq, Email: dr.bahirrazzaq@uomustansiriya.edu.iq, orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4421-8690>

Dalya Basil Hanna, Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences/ College of Pharmacy/ Mustansiriya University, Baghdad, Iraq, email: pharm.dr.dalyabasil@uomustansiriya.edu.iq, orcid :<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3201-4303>

Ghaith Ali Jasim, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology/ College of Pharmacy/ Mustansiriya University, Baghdad, Iraq, email: pharm.ghaithali@uomustansiriya.edu.iq ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5153-4094>

Received: 04/26/2021 Accepted: 07/15/2022 Published: 07/25/2022 DOI:<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7348884>

Abstract

Hepatocellular proliferation is one of the leading causes of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), and is a widely distributed type of cancer-related death. There are considerable challenges in treating hepatocellular carcinoma, including ineffectiveness, adverse effects, and drug resistance to available drugs. It has been established that a high intake of Brassica vegetables is linked to a lower risk of many cancers. In the study, Brassica nigra seeds were extracted; phytochemical analysis of the extract was done, including phytochemical screening tests and Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis. Antiproliferative activity of hydroalcoholic Brassica seeds extract has been studied at 800mg/kg and compared with the control group (given normal saline), phenobarbital group (Phenobarbital 75mg/kg), and combination group (Brassica extract 800mg/kg+ Phenobarbital 75mg/kg). The GC-MS analysis revealed the presence of the isothiocyanate compound. Compared to the phenobarbital group, Combining groups pretreated with Brassica nigra seeds for 14 days and phenobarbital for seven days caused a significant reduction in Ki67 and Bcl2 expression that was obvious in immunohistochemical slides. Also, combination groups showed a substantial decrease in the expression level of genes related to the cell cycle, including minichromosome maintenance genes 2 (Mcm2) and cyclin A2 (Ccna2), and a significant reduction in the expression level of Cytochrome P450, including CYP2B10 and CYP2C29 in comparison with phenobarbital group. Brassica nigra seeds extract showed antiproliferative and apoptotic effects on the liver tissue, suggesting it has a beneficial impact on minimizing the risk of liver cancer.

Keywords: Hepatocellular proliferation, Phenobarbital, Brassica seeds.

Resumen

La proliferación hepatocelular es una de las principales causas de carcinoma hepatocelular (HCC) y es un tipo de muerte relacionada con el cáncer ampliamente distribuido. Existen desafíos considerables en el tratamiento del carcinoma hepatocelular, incluida la ineficacia, los efectos adversos y la resistencia a los medicamentos disponibles. Se ha establecido que un alto consumo de vegetales Brassica está relacionado con un menor riesgo de muchos tipos de cáncer. En el estudio se extrajeron semillas de Brassica nigra; Se realizó un análisis fitoquímico del extracto, incluidas pruebas de selección fitoquímica y análisis de cromatografía de gases-espectrometría de masas (GC-MS). La actividad antiproliferativa del extracto hidroalcohólico de semillas de Brassica se estudió a 800 mg/kg y se comparó con el grupo de control (administrado con solución salina normal), el grupo de fenobarbital (fenobarbital 75 mg/kg) y el grupo combinado (extracto de Brassica 800 mg/kg + fenobarbital 75 mg/kg). El análisis GC-MS reveló la presencia del compuesto de isotiocianato. En comparación con el grupo de fenobarbital, la combinación de grupos pretratados con semillas de Brassica nigra durante 14 días y fenobarbital durante siete días provocó una reducción significativa en la expresión de Ki67 y Bcl2 que fue evidente en los portaobjetos inmunohistoquímicos. Además, los grupos de combinación mostraron una disminución sustancial en el nivel de expresión de genes relacionados con el ciclo celular, incluidos los genes de mantenimiento de minicromosomas 2 (Mcm2) y ciclina A2 (Ccna2), y una reducción significativa en el nivel de expresión de Citocromo P450, incluidos CYP2B10 y CYP2C29 en comparación con el grupo fenobarbital. El extracto de semillas de Brassica nigra mostró efectos antiproliferativos y apoptóticos en el tejido hepático, lo que sugiere que tiene un impacto beneficioso para minimizar el riesgo de cáncer de hígado.

Palabras clave: Proliferación hepatocelular, Fenobarbital, Semillas de Brassica.

Introduction

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a cancer which begins in the liver, it is considered the most widespread form of primary liver cancer, most commonly occurs in patients with chronic liver disorders, like cirrhosis, infection by hepatitis C or B virus¹. It is widely agreed that hepatocarcinogenesis is very complicated disease and arises during the malignant transformation of normal hepatocytes via a multi-stage biological process in which numerous variables are involved, particularly genetic and epigenetic alterations².

Classically, HCC appears and develops in silent manner, making its detection difficult before the later stage of disease development³. Hepatocellular carcinoma is among cancers that have poor prognosis because this malignancy resists the majority of chemotherapeutic treatments⁴. Sorafenib and lenvatinib still considered as single-drug regimens that are highly effective^{5,6}. Chemoprevention of cancer with natural phytochemical constituents is a revolutionary technique for stopping, or curing cancer⁷. In several years have been seeing that high consuming of Brassicaceae vegetables minimize the risk of a large number of cancers, like lung⁸, gastrointestinal tract^{9,10}, prostate¹¹ and bladder cancers¹²⁻¹⁴. The aim of this study was evaluation of the effect of Brassica nigra seeds extract against hepatocellular proliferation induced by phenobarbital, as tumor- promoting agent.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and reagents: Chloroform where purchased from British drug house, UK. Ethanol 99 from Alpha chemo, India. Formaldehyde PanReac Applichem, USA. Na₂HPO₄ and NaH₂PO₄ from Fluca, Germany. Paraffin wax and Xylene from Scharlau, Spain. Phenobarbital ampoule (200mg/ml) supplied from Samarth life sciences PVT.LTD, India. From Elabscience Biotechnology-USA purchased the followings: Bcl2 Monoclonal Antibody, Ki-67 Monoclonal Antibody and Step plus Poly-HRP Anti Mouse/Rabbit IgG detection system, while RNA extraction kit, Transcript One-step gDNA Removal and cDNA Synthesis SuperMix kit and Trans Start Tip Green qPCR SuperMix were purchased from TRANS Company in china. Five genes (forward and reverse primers) were employed in this study, supplied by Bioneer, Korea manufacturer with sequences as follows:

MCM2: TCACGGTGCGCCACATCGAG, and CC-GGGCAAAGTCTTGCGCA

CCNA2: TACCCCCAGAAGTAGCAG, and GGGTCAG-CATCTATCAAAC

CYP2B10: 59-CAGGTGATCGGCTCACACC-39, and 59-TGACTGCATCTGAGTATGGCATT-39

CYP2C29: 59-GGGCTCAAAGCCTACTGTCA-39, and 59-AACGCCAAAACCTTTAA-39 Housekeeping gene that used in the current study was GAPDH: CGGGTTCCTATA-AATACGGACTG, and CCAATACGGGCCAAATCCGTTT.

The plant: Brassica nigra seeds were collected from Baghdad/Alshorga local market in September 2020, then it had

been successfully identified by professional plant taxonomists in the Department of Pharmacognosy/ Collage of Pharmacy/ Mustansiriyah University, and in the Collage of Science/ University of Baghdad, then seeds had stored in dark place few days prior to extraction process.

Animals: Twenty eight, non-previously treated male Swiss albino mice aged (8weeks) their weight (25±5) gm provided from Iraqi Center for Cancer Research were retained in well ventilated place with woodchip bedding with well-marked by their tails for identification and were maintained under standard conditions of relative humidity (70±5%). Temperature (25 ± 2°C), and a 12-hour light-dark cycle with free access to water and food (pellets) in the animal house of the Collage of Pharmacy/ Mustansiriyah University.

Extract preparation: Brassica nigra seeds (2000g) were air dried and finely grinded by electrical mill. These seeds were subjected to extraction by reflux extraction processes. Firstly, the powdered seeds had been immersed with absolute ethanol (99%) and water at 70:30 percent in round reflux apparatus at a temperature range from 50-55°C for 1hr, after that the seeds residues were filtered using filter paper to get clean crude extract. Finally, the filtrate undergo evaporation by a rotary evaporator and further air drying till a semisolid paste was obtained. The extract that obtained at weight 140gm was labelled and preserved in a sealed glass container in refrigerator at 4°C till the time of experiment. The yield of extract was found to be 7% (w/w) according to the following equation¹⁵.

The yield of extract = Weight of material obtained /Weight of starting material × 100.

Phytochemical screening: Phytochemical screening of hydro alcoholic extract of Brassica nigra using standard procedure for detection the presence of glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponin, tannin and phenols¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS analysis): This technique commonly used for both qualitative and quantitative analysis of a sample containing a variety of organic compounds¹⁸. The GC-MS technique was used in the current study to recognize the phytoconstituents present in the Brassica nigra extract. This work was done in the Ministry of Science and Technology, Environment and Water Department. The GC-MS was carried out using a Shimadzu (QP2010) PLUS system. The column used in GC-MS system was (optima-5ms, Medium non polar 30m length, 0.25 um thickness). The chemical compounds from the Brassica nigra extract were known by comparing between the retention times of the obtained chromatographic peaks.

Animal grouping: Twenty eight male Swiss albino mice were randomly divided into four groups (n=7 for each): First group (Control group): received normal saline by oral gavage for one week and continue with normal saline intraperitoneally for the second week. Second group (Phenobarbital group): received normal saline by oral gavage for one week, then intraperitoneal phenobarbital at 75mg/kg /day for the second week. Third group (Extract alone group): received the extract at dose 800mg/kg/day by oral gavage for one week, then

continue with extract at dose 800mg/kg/day by oral gavage for the second week. Fourth group (Combination group): received the Brassica nigra extract at dose 800mg/kg/day by oral gavage for one week, then continued with Brassica nigra extract at dose 800mg/kg/day by oral gavage with intraperitoneal phenobarbital at 75mg/kg /day for the second week.

Liver harvest: After the ending of treatment period, animals were euthanized by placed in a container that contained the chloroform. To ensure circulation, the chemical was soaked in cotton wool and placed in the container for 5 minutes before to exposure and liver tissues were collected surgically.

Immunohistochemistry analysis: The liver tissues transferred in buffered formalin (100 ml of 40% formalin+900 ml distilled water+4 gm of sodium di-hydrogen phosphate+6.5 gm of sodium phosphate dibasic). After fixation, the tissue samples were immersed in ascending grades of ethanol to avoid excessive tissue hardening to prepare the sample for the next step as a following procedure (Eighty percent ethanol for 15 minutes, Ninety five percent ethanol for 15 minutes), Absolute ethanol (99.9%) for 15 minutes. Chloroform for 15 minutes. Then Paraffin wax was molted at 60°C for 15 minutes^{19,20}. Finally, samples were labeled and inserted in paraffin wax as a blocks that prepared to immunohistochemistry analysis of Ki67 and Bcl2 expression under standard protocol^{21,22}. To assess the fraction of immunolabeled cells in liver specimens from each animal included in the current study, the labeling index expressed as the percentage of positive cells out of the total number of cells were counted in five area that randomly selected with 100, 400 magnification per each section from every mouse. The percentage of Ki-67 positive cells was graded as 0 for negative staining, 1 for weak staining, 2 for moderate staining, and 3 for strong staining. The degree of intensity (which indicates the concentration of the stain in positive cells) was graded as (0) for negative staining and +, ++, and +++ for weak, moderate, and strong intensity, respectively. The following scores was used to calculate the percentages of Ki67 positive cells: 1+ (weak) Means less than 10%, 2+ (moderate) = 11 to 50%, and 3+ (strong) = more than 50%²³. Bcl2 staining intensity was rated on a 5-point scale: 0 represented no staining; 1+ represented weak staining; 2+ represented moderate staining; 3+ represented strong staining; and 4+ represented intense immunostaining. The following scores was used to calculate the percentages of Bcl2 positive cells: 0 (no staining); 1+ mean 1 to 25% cells stained positive; 2+ mean 26 to 50% cells stained positive; 3+ mean 51 to 75% cells stained positive; 4+ mean 76 to 100% cells stained positive²⁴.

Gene expression analysis: Firstly 50- 100 gm of the liver tissue transferred into Eppendorf tubes which contained 1ml of triazole, then stored in deep freeze until assay for gene expression investigations. Using RNA extraction kit (transcript)²⁵, RNA was obtained then cDNA were synthesized from total RNA using cDNA synthesis supermix (transcript) kit²⁶ and were amplified using the sets of primers. In this study the q RT-PCR was used to quantify for four genes (MCM2, CCNA2, CYP2B10 and CYP2C29) according to manufacture protocol. The final solution was placed in RT-PCR system for

thermal reaction. Table (1) shows the thermal cycling protocol with suitable melting point for each primer according to manufacturer protocol²⁷.

Step	Temperature	Time	Cycle
Denaturation	94 °C	5 sec	40
Annealing	50-60 °C	15 sec	40
Extension	72 °C	10 sec	40

Calculations

The cycle threshold (CT) of genes of interest was normalized to that of internal control gene. The difference in the cycle threshold (Ct) values between the GAPDH (internal control gene) and the interest genes include: MCM2, CCNA2, CYP2B10 and CYP2C29, was calculated as the following equation²⁸:

$$\Delta CT (\text{test}) = CT \text{ gene of interest (test)} - CT \text{ internal control}$$

Calibrator was chosen from the control samples, DCT of calibrator was calculated according to following equation:

$$\Delta CT (\text{calibrator}) = CT \text{ gene of interest (test)} - CT \text{ internal control}$$

The DCT of the test samples was normalized to the DCT of the calibrator:DD CT was calculated according to the following equation: $\Delta\Delta CT = \Delta CT (\text{test}) - \Delta CT (\text{calibrator})$ Finally, the expression ratio was calculated according to the formula: $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT} = \text{Normalized expression ratio}$ ²⁸.

Statistical analysis: The statistical analysis of this prospective study was performed with the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 24.0 and Microsoft Excel 2020. Categorical data formulated as count and percentage. Chi-square, Kruskal Wallis and Mann Whitney tests were used to describe the association of these data. Numerical data were described as mean and standard error. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for comparison among more than two groups. P- Value <0.05 considered as a significant difference.

Results

Phytochemical screening tests: In this study, the yield percentage of the Brassica nigra seeds extract was 7%, since 140 gm was obtained from 2000gm of Brassica nigra seeds. Qualitative phytochemical studies were performed on the hydro alcoholic extract of Brassica nigra seeds to determine the presence of various phytochemical constituents. The results showed the presence of glycosides, alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, phenols, tannin, saponin and coumarin, table (2).

Chemical	Result	Chemical	Result
Alkaloids	+	Terpenoids	+
Flavonoids	+	Glycosides	+
Saponin	+	Cumarin	+
Tannins, Phenols	++		

(+): present, (++) : highly present

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis: The most important recognized chemicals were isothiocyanates like allyl and butyl isothiocyanate. Figures (1) showed the peaks of these chemicals.

Figure 1. (A) GC-MS analysis results of Brassica nigra hydro alcoholic seeds extract. (B) Isothiocyanate compound detected by GC-MS.

Regarding the immunohistochemical expression of Ki-67 and Bcl2 in mice hepatic tissues, the results of the present study showed that there was a significant difference (P value= 0.001) in the staining intensity between control group and both phenobarbital and combination group, while there was no significant difference in staining intensity between control group and extract group for Ki-67 (P value=0.317) table (3) and for Bcl2 (P value=0.606), table (4).

Table 3. Frequency distribution of immunohistochemical expression of Ki-67 in studied groups.

Ki-67		Study groups			
		Control	Phenobarbital	Extract	Combination
IHC score	0	7 (100%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (100%)	0 (0.00%)
	+	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (71.44%)
	++	0 (0.00%)	1 (14.28%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (14.28%)
	+++	0 (0.00%)	6 (85.72%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (14.28%)
Total		7 (100%)	7 (100%)	7 (100%)	7 (100%)
P-value		-	0.001	0.317	0.001
			-	0.001	0.001
				-	0.001

Table 4. Frequency distribution of immunohistochemical expression of Bcl2 in studied groups.

Bcl2		Study groups			
		Control	Phenobarbital	Extract	Combination
IHC score	0	7 (100%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (85.72%)	4 (57.15%)
	+	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
	++	0 (0.00%)	1 (14.28%)	1 (14.28%)	1 (14.28%)
	+++	0 (0.00%)	1 (14.28%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (14.28%)
	++++	0 (0.00%)	5 (71.44%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (14.28%)
Total		7 (100%)	7 (100%)	7 (100%)	7 (100%)
P-value		-	0.001	0.606	0.001
			-	0.001	0.001
				-	0.001

Effect of hydro alcoholic seeds extract of Brassica nigra on gene expression depending on real time reverse transcriptase poly chain reaction (qRT-PCR): The results of the present study clarified that mean expression levels of Mcm2 gene showed a significant elevation in phenobarbital group ($p < 0.05$) when compared with control groups, and also with both extract and combination groups (figure (4-A)), the last three groups did not showed any significant difference among each ($p > 0.05$). Also, the mean expression levels of Ccna2 gene showed a markedly elevation within phenobarbital group ($p < 0.05$) when compared with other studied groups, where the mean expression levels of Ccna2 gene were lowered significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the extract and combination group when compared with phenobarbital group. However no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in mean expression levels of Ccna2 were detected upon treating with Brassica nigra seeds extract compared with control group or combination protocol, figure(4-B). Regarding the mean expression levels of CYP2B10 gene, there was a significant elevation within phenobarbital group ($p < 0.05$) when compared with control, extract and combination group, where there was no statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in mean expression levels of CYP2B10 gene among the last three groups (figure 4-C). Considering CYP2C29 gene, mean expression

levels were significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated in phenobarbital group when compared other studied groups. Also, there was no statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in mean expression levels of CYP2C29 gene among control, extract, and combination group, figure (4-D).

Figure 4. Effect of hydro alcoholic Brassica nigra seeds extract on gene expression. (A): Mcm2 expression, (B): Ccna2 expression, (C): CYP2B10 expression, (D): CYP2C29. Data were expressed as means \pm SEM. Different small letters (a, b) represent significant differences among the examined groups. P- Value < 0.05 indicate a significant difference.

Discussion

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) still the most widespread form of primary liver cancer and a major cause of cancer-correlated death around the world²⁹. By 2030, the global burden of HCC mortality is expected to reach one million deaths per year³⁰. It has been established that a high intake of Brassica vegetables is linked to a lower risk of cancer, this link clearly appears in lung, stomach, colon, rectal and prostate cancer³¹⁻³³. In the present study, the percent of yield from Brassica nigra seed was 7%, using water- ethanol solvent system, according to the reflux extraction method^{34,35}. This result was higher than others which were conducted by Nitin Kumar (2011)³⁶ who used methanol as solvent (4.3% w/w) and Anand P. (2014)³⁷ that was 5.18 % (w/w) using DW as a solvent and Basha S. (2015)³⁸ that was 1.4% (w/w) using DW and 6.52 % (w/w) using methanol.

This finding largely related to the extraction process, since the isolation of bioactive chemicals from plant materials using different temperatures during extraction technique is very important, where the findings of previous research revealed that increasing temperature can increase the yield of extrac-

tion for *Brassica nigra* and this support the current results³⁹. The present study aimed to investigate the phytochemicals of *Brassica nigra* seeds extract. The results showed that the plant contains flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenes, saponins, tannins and glycosides, these classes of chemical compounds were same to those of previous studies conducted by Uddin MS. (2020)⁴⁰, Danlami U. (2016)⁴¹, and Basha S. (2015)⁴². In the current study, GC-MS analysis confirmed the presence of isothiocyanates represented by 3-butenylisothiocyanate and methyl isocyanate. The present study come in accordance with sharma et al. (2018) who detect the same isothiocyanate compounds from *Brassica juncea* (a plant with same family of *Brassica nigra*), since isothiocyanate present in abundance within Brassicaceae family⁴³.

In the present study, ki-67 expression was measured due to its intense association with mitotic phase of cell cycle compared to other proliferating proteins, where Ki-67 expression reach its maximum level at G2/M phases⁴⁴. The finding of the current research showed a significant elevation in the nuclear expression of Ki-67 after treatment with intraperitoneal PB compared with control group. Phenobarbital is known as CAR activator agent, so the activation of these receptors in liver caused hepatocyte hypertrophy and hyperplasia. The nuclear protein "Ki-67" is largely accompanying with tumor cell growth and proliferation⁴⁴.

This study was in accordance with a study done by Shizu R. (2013) who reported a significant increase in Ki-67 levels within mice hepatic tissue following phenobarbital administration depending on IHC technique⁴⁴. Treatment with *Brassica nigra* seeds extract in the present study interestingly reduced the percentage of Ki-67 positive cells, suggesting inhibition of hepatocyte proliferation. The suspected mechanism of *Brassica nigra* in reduced hepatocyte proliferation is related to isothiocyanate compounds which are produced by hydrolysis of their precursor molecules glucosinolates, one of the active substances in *Brassica nigra* that has shown potential anti-tumor activity represented by sulforaphane, allyl isothiocyanates (AITC) and indole-3-carbinol⁴⁵. Also, Vrca et al. study proved that *Brassica nigra* extract have a potent antiproliferative action against different human cancer cell lines⁴⁶.

Regarding Bcl-2, overexpression and phosphorylation of this protein, which is the most significant anti-apoptotic marker. Considering the results of the current study, PB alone group exhibited a significant reduction in the apoptosis process, represented by Bcl-2 overexpression. Supporting of this result comes from previous research done by Sanders S. (1999) who indicated that mice taken phenobarbital in the food have high expression level of Bcl-2, as anti-apoptotic protein⁴⁷. A high rate of apoptosis in the liver tissue has been linked to a lower risk of hepatocyte proliferation and hepatic carcinoma. In this study, the hydroalcoholic *Brassica nigra* seeds extract stimulated apoptosis in liver tissue within combination group (*Brassica nigra* plus phenobarbital) compared to phenobarbital alone group, represented by a significant decline in Bcl-2 protein expression according to the IHC technique. De Felipe also showed that sulforaphane, a compound found in *Brassica nigra*, have an ability of increasing mitochondrial

apoptosis through suppression of Bcl-2 protein⁴⁸. The seeds of *Brassica nigra* contain sinigrin in high amounts⁴⁹, a previous study done by Jie et al. (2014) observed that sinigrin have ability to cause Bcl-2 down regulation, which support the finding of the present study⁴⁹.

In this study, the proliferation was successively induced by phenobarbital that confirmed by a significant hepatic up-regulation of cell cycle-related genes named minichromosome maintenance gene 2 (Mcm2) and Cyclin A2 (Ccna2) in phenobarbital group compared with control. These findings were closely agreed with a study done by Shizu et al. (2013) who successively proved that mice treated with PB (1000 ppm) in diet for one week accelerate cell cycle through initiation of DNA synthesis as a consequence of elevated levels of cell proliferation markers, including Mcm2 and Ccna2 that were up-regulated in S-phase and m-phase, respectively⁴⁴.

The findings of the present study showed a down regulation of Ccna2 gene in combination group significantly compared with phenobarbital group, so the Ccna2 protein cannot contributes with driving the entry into cell cycle, cannot binds to CDK2 in S-phase and cannot binds to CDK1 in G2/M phase of cell cycle. Similarly, significant down regulation of Mcm2 gene was observed in this group that suggest a cell cycle arrest. Therefore, and according to the present findings, down regulation of Ccna2 and Mcm2 proteins after *Brassica nigra* seeds extract treatment led to cell cycle arresting at S-phase and G2/M phase with inhibition of DNA replication that will lead to block their entrance into mitotic phases. Since combination group showed decreasing in Ccna2 and Mcm2 expression compared to phenobarbital group, this result can confirm the antiproliferative action of *Brassica nigra* seeds extract on hepatocytes which induced by phenobarbital.

The current finding agreed with cell line study done by Ahmed et al. (2020) which stated that the *Brassica nigra* seeds extract has significant proliferation inhibitory effect in A549 and H1299 lung cancer cells, so these cell lines were stopped at S and G2/M phase by *Brassica nigra* seeds extract in comparison with control cells⁵⁰, supporting the results of the current study about *Brassica nigra* anti-proliferative activity. In a previous research, allyl isothiocyanate, and as one of *Brassica nigra* seeds components, was shown to have growth-inhibitory action against lung cells proliferation and carcinoma⁵¹. The precise phytochemicals in *Brassica nigra* seeds extract that responsible for the reported anti-proliferative effect are unknown at this time, so further researches are essential since seeds are reported to contain number of bioactive chemicals. The results of the current study were supported by a study done by Jie et al. (2014) who stated the antiproliferative activity of sinigrin against liver damage induced by carcinogenic substances in rats via cell cycle arrest⁴⁹. Previous studies indicated that allyl isothiocyanate, a major component of *Brassica nigra* seed, has been found to have antiproliferative properties in a variety of cancer types^{52,53}.

Cytochrome P4502B (CYP2B) and 2C (CYP2C) protein levels were measured in this study to evaluate CYP expression, as expected, the fold of expression of CYP2B10 gene was

higher in phenobarbital group than others, since phenobarbital is CYP2B inducer and CYP2B10 is highly induced by PB, this finding was in line with Cartea et al. results⁵⁴. In this study, CYP2B10 expression declined significantly in combination group, this finding is in line with a prior research, which found that exposure to glucosinolates, the major metabolite of *Brassica nigra* inhibited phase I enzymes⁵⁵. Cytochrome P2C29 is one of CAR target genes⁵⁶, as reported previously by Hecht⁵⁷ and Fahey et al.⁵⁸, where CYP2C29 mRNA level was also elevated after PB exposure, this finding was in accordance with the result of the present study. In vitro and in vivo researches have stated that glucosinolate influence many stages of cancer development, comprising the inhibition of enzymes activation, including phase I enzymes⁵⁸⁻⁶².

As a future work, the following points can be suggested: The precise active phytochemicals of *Brassica nigra* that responsible for the observed effects are unknown, so fractionation of the extract, isolation and purification of active constituents is essential. Evaluate the in vitro and in vivo anticancer effect of the *Brassica nigra* extract on different cells and tissues using tumor-initiator agents, and try to understand the molecular mechanism and exact signaling pathway. Further researches may require to ensure the safety and tolerability of *Brassica nigra* extracts.

Conclusions

In this study, reflux extraction method using water: ethanol solvent system gave acceptable percent of yield, and the major active phytochemicals may be represented by isothiocyanate, depending on GC-MS analysis. *Brassica nigra* extract showed a remarkable antiproliferative and apoptotic effect confirmed by immunohistochemistry results (ki67, Bcl2). Real time qRT-PCR results further indicated the proposed mechanism of the antiproliferative effect of extract represented by its down regulation on the critical cell cycle genes (Mcm2 and Ccna2) within hepatocyte cells. The extract has inhibitory action on CYP2B10 and CYP2C29 expression which may be useful in protection against carcinogens activated by these enzymes.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Mustansiriyah University (www.uomustansiriyah.edu.iq), Baghdad, Iraq, for its support in the present work.

Source of funding: there is no funding.

Conflict of interest: there is no conflict of interest.

References

1. Issues CC. Current Clinical Issues Liver Cancer on the Rise TO. 2005;1029–32.
2. Yoon SK. Molecular mechanism of hepatocellular carcinoma. *Hepatoma Res.* 2018;4(8):42.
3. Bialecki ES, Di Bisceglie AM. Diagnosis of hepatocellular carcinoma.

Hpb. 2005;7(1):26–34.

4. Sukowati CHC, Rosso N, Crocè LS, Tiribelli C. Hepatic cancer stem cells and drug resistance: Relevance in targeted therapies for hepatocellular carcinoma. *World J Hepatol.* 2010;2(3):114–26.
5. Llovet JM, Kelley RK, Villanueva A, Singal AG, Pikarsky E, Roayaie S, et al. Hepatocellular carcinoma. *Nat Rev Dis Prim [Internet].* 2021;7(1). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41572-020-00240-3>
6. de Rosamel L, Blanc JF. Emerging tyrosine kinase inhibitors for the treatment of hepatocellular carcinoma. *Expert Opin Emerg Drugs [Internet].* 2017;22(2):175–90. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14728214.2017.1336538>
7. Wege H, Li J, Ittrich H. Treatment Lines in Hepatocellular Carcinoma. *Visc Med.* 2019;35(4):266–72.
8. London SJ, Yuan JM, Chung FL, Gao YT, Coetzee GA, Ross RK, et al. Isothiocyanates, glutathione S-transferase M1 and T1 polymorphisms, and lung-cancer risk: A prospective study of men in Shanghai, China. *Lancet.* 2000;356(9231):724–9.
9. Smith TK, Lund EK, Clarke RG, Bennett RN, Johnson IT. Effects of Brussels sprout juice on the cell cycle and adhesion of human colorectal carcinoma cells (HT29) in vitro. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2005;53(10):3895–901.
10. Van Poppel G, Verhoeven DTH, Verhagen H, Goldbohm RA. Brassica vegetables and cancer prevention: Epidemiology and mechanisms. *Adv Exp Med Biol.* 2000;472:159–68.
11. Giovannucci E, Rimm EB, Liu Y, Stampfer MJ, Willett WC. A Prospective Study of Cruciferous Vegetables and Prostate Cancer. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2003;12(12):1403–9.
12. Abbaoui B, Lucas CR, Riedl KM, Clinton SK, Mortazavi A. Cruciferous Vegetables, Isothiocyanates, and Bladder Cancer Prevention. *Mol Nutr Food Res.* 2018;62(18):1–14.
13. Zhao H, Lin J, Grossman HB, Hernandez LM, Dinney CP, Wu X. Dietary isothiocyanates, GSTM1, GSTT1, NAT2 polymorphisms and bladder cancer risk. *Int J Cancer.* 2007;120(10):2208–13.
14. Mastuo T, Miyata Y, Yuno T, Mukae Y, Otsubo A, Mitsunari K, et al. Molecular mechanisms of the anti-cancer effects of isothiocyanates from cruciferous vegetables in bladder cancer. *Molecules.* 2020;25(3).
15. Omoja V, Ihedioha T, Eke G, PeterAjuzie I, Okezie S. Evaluation of the acute toxicity, phytochemical constituents and anti-ulcer properties of methanolic leaf extract of *Annona muricata* in mice. *J Intercult Ethnopharmacol.* 2014;3(1):37.
16. Evans W.C. Trease and Evan's Pharmacognosy. Harourt Publishers, London, ISBN: 0702026174, 336-337.
17. Harborne J.B. Phytochemical methods: A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis. London, Chapman and Hall, 2007; ISBN: 81-8128-410-4, 1-34.
18. Khalaf HA, Mahdi MF, and Abaas IS. Preliminary Phytochemical and GC-MS analysis of chemical constituents of Iraqi *Plantago lanceolata* L. *Al-Mustansiriyah Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences (AJPS)* (2018); 18.2: 114-121..
19. Anthony L. Junqueira's Basic Histology text and atlas. Edition. McGraw-Hill Education. 2016
20. Alaa HO, Mshimesh BA, Mohsin RA. Studying the Toxicity of Hydroalcoholic Caraway Seeds Extract in Female Rats. *Al-Mus-*

21. Alzaini A, Abbas WA, Alzubbaidi SH, Aljaleeli AN, Almugda-di SF. Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF-C) Protein Expression Related with Lymphangiogenesis in Iraqi Cervical Cancer Patients. *Al-Mustansiriyah Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences (AJPS)* (2019); 19.4: 28-40.
22. Elabscience.Immunohistochemistry kit protocol.Available from: techsupport@elabscience.comtechsupport@elab-science.com, other: www.elabscience.comwww.elabscience.com
23. Al-Ghamdi TH, Shafek Atta I. Efficacy of interleukin-6 in the induction of liver cell proliferation after hemi-hepatectomy: his-topathologic and immunohistochemical study. *Int J Clin Exp Pathol* [Internet]. 2020;13(7):1540–9. Available from: www.ijcep.com/
24. Krajewska M, Krajewski S, Epstein JI, Shabaik A, Sauvageot J, Song K, et al. Immunohistochemical analysis of bcl-2, bax, bcl-X, and mcl-1 expression in prostate cancers. *Am J Pathol*. 1996;148(5):1567–76.
25. Trans,RNA extraction protocol, Available from: www.transgen-biotech.com, other info@ transgenbiotech.com
26. Trans,Transcript one step gDNA removal and cDNA synthe-sis protocol, Available from: www.transgenbiotech.com, other info@ transgenbiotech.com
27. Trans,qPCR protocol, Available from: www.transgenbiotech.com, other info@ transgenbiotech.com
28. Livak K, Piña A. Analysis of Relative Gene Expression Data Us-ing Real-Time Quantitative PCR and the 2– $\Delta\Delta$ CT Method Re-lated papers Analysis of Relat ive Gene Expression Dat a Using Real-T ime Quant it at ive PCR and t he 2 C T M.... *Methods* [In-ternet]. 2001;25(4):402–8. Available from: www.idealibrary.com
29. Balogh J, Ili DV, Gordon S, Li X, Ghobrial RM, Jr HPM. Jhc-3-041. *J Hepatocell Carcinoma* [Internet]. 2016; Volume 3:41–53. Available from: <https://www.dovepress.com/hepatocellular-carcinoma-a-review-peer-reviewed-article-JHC>.
30. Kim E, Viatour P. Hepatocellular carcinoma: old friends and new tricks. *Exp Mol Med* [Internet]. 2020;52(12):1898–907. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s12276-020-00527-1>.
31. Mishra V, Mishra M, Chaudhari BP, Khanna R, Das M. Arge-mone Oil and Butter Yellow Induced Toxicity in Hepatic and Ex-tra Hepatic Tissues. *Bioenergetics* 3: 111. doi: 10.4172/2167-7662.1000111 Page 2 of 7 Volume 3• Issue 1• 1000111 Bio-energetics ISSN: 2167-7662 BEG an open access journal adenine dinucleotide phosphate reduced (NADPH), bovine serum albumin (BSA) were purchased from Sigma Chemical Company, St. Louis, MO, USA. *Argemone mexicana*. 2014.
32. Verhoeven DTH, Goldbohm RA, Van Poppel G, Verhagen H, Van Den Brandt PA. Epidemiological studies on Brassica veg-etables and cancer risk. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev*. 1996;5(9):733–48.
33. Kristal AR. Brassica vegetables and prostate cancer risk: A re-view of the epidemiologic evidence. *Pharm Biol*. 2002; 40(SUP-PL.):55–8.
34. Nandini T, Ramya Sree D, Janbee S, Siva Sai Kiran K, Raveen-dra Babu G. Study of immunomodulatory effect of seeds of *Brassica nigra* and *Cuminum cyminum* in albino rats. *Int J Pharm Clin Res*. 2016;8(1):10–4.
35. Kinghorn AD, Ren Y, Li J, Sung CK. Cancer chemopreventive activity of higher plants. *Plant Bioactives and Drug Discovery: Principles, Practice, and Perspectives*. 2012 Apr 6:337-57.
36. Upwar N, Patel R, Waseem N, Mahobia N. In vitro anthelmintic activity of *Brassica nigra* Linn. seeds. (2011).
37. Anand P, Murali YK, Tandon V, Murthy PS, Chandra R. Insuli-notropic effect of aqueous extract of *Brassica nigra* improves glucose homeostasis in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *Exp Clin Endocrinol Diabetes*. 2009;117(6):251–6.
38. Basha SN, Rekha R, Saleh S, Yemane S. Evaluation of invitro anthelmintic activities of *Brassica nigra*, *Ocimum basilicum* and *Rumex abyssinicus*. *Pharmacogn J*. 2011;3(20):88–92.
39. Radha Krishnan K, Azhagu Saravana Babu P, Babuskin S, Si-varajan M, Sukumar M. Modeling the Kinetics of Antioxidant Extraction from *Origanum vulgare* and *Brassica nigra*. *Chem Eng Commun*. 2015;202(12):1577–85.
40. Uddin MS, Millat MS, Islam MS, Hussain MS, Uddin MG, Sid-diqui SA, et al. Exploration of in vitro thrombolytic, anthelmin-thic, cytotoxic and in vivo anxiolytic potentials with phytochemi-cal screening of flowers of *Brassica nigra*. *Futur J Pharm Sci*. 2020;6(1).
41. Danlami U. Phytochemical, Nutritional and Antimicrobial Evalu-ations of the Aqueous Extract of *Brassica Nigra* (Brassicaceae) Seeds. 2016; 4(4):161.
42. Basha SN, Rekha R, Saleh S, Yemane S. Evaluation of invitro anthelmintic activities of *Brassica nigra*, *Ocimum basilicum* and *Rumex abyssinicus*. *Pharmacogn J*. 2011;3(20):88–92.
43. Sharma A, Rai PK, Prasad S. GC–MS detection and determi-nation of major volatile compounds in *Brassica juncea* L. leaves and seeds. *Microchem J* [Internet]. 2018;138(2017):488–93. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2018.01.015>
44. Shizu R, Benoki S, Numakura Y, Kodama S, Miyata M, Yam-azoe Y, et al. Xenobiotic-Induced Hepatocyte Proliferation As-sociated with Constitutive Active/Androstane Receptor (CAR) or Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor α (PPAR α) Is Enhanced by Pregnane X Receptor (PXR) Activation in Mice. *PLoS One*. 2013;8(4).
45. Dzulkipli FA, Mashor MY, Jaafar H. An overview of recent counting methods for Ki67 IHC staining. *J Biomed Clin Sci*. 2018;3(2):10–7.
46. Vrca I, Šćurla J, Kević N, Burčul F, Čulić FC, Bočina I, Blažević I, et al. Influence of isolation techniques on the com-position of glucosinolate breakdown products, their antiprolif-erative activity and gastrointestinal stability of allyl isothiocya-nate. *Eur Food Res Technol* (2022); 248, 567–576. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-021-03903-x>
47. Sanders S, Thorgeirsson SS. Phenobarbital promotes liver growth in c-myc/TGF- α transgenic mice by inducing hypertro-phy and inhibiting apoptosis. *Carcinogenesis*. 1999;20(1):41–9.
48. de Felipe Junior F. Isothiocyanates in cancer – Sulforaphane and their relatives. 2007;520–30
49. Jie M, Cheung WM, Yu V, Zhou Y, Tong PH, Ho JWS. Anti-proliferative activities of sinigrin on carcinogen-induced hepato-toxicity in rats. *PLoS One*. 2014;9(10):1–9.
50. Ahmed AG, Hussein UK, Ahmed AE, Kim KM, Mahmoud HM, Hammouda O, et al. Mustard Seed (*Brassica nigra*) Extract Ex-hibits Antiproliferative Effect against Human Lung Cancer Cells through Differential Regulation of Apoptosis, Cell Cycle, Migra-

tion, and Invasion. *Molecules* [Internet] 2020;25(9):2069. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/molecules25092069>

51. Tripathi K, Hussein UK, Anupalli R, Barnett R, Bachaboina L, Scalici J, et al. Allyl isothiocyanate induces replication-associated DNA damage response in NSCLC cells and sensitizes to ionizing radiation. *Oncotarget*. 2015;6(7):5237–52.
52. Zhang Y. Allyl isothiocyanate as a cancer chemopreventive phytochemical. *Mol Nutr Food Res*. 2010;54(1):127–35.
53. Li L, Bao X, Zhang QY, Negishi M, Ding X. Role of Cyp2b in phenobarbital-induced hepatocyte proliferation in mice. *Drug Metab Dispos*. 2017;45(8):977–81.
54. Cartea ME, Velasco P. Glucosinolates in Brassica foods: Bioavailability in food and significance for human health. *Phytochem Rev*. 2008;7(2):213–29.
55. Dusek J, Skoda J, Holas O, Horvatova A, Smutny T, Linhartova L, et al. Stilbene compound trans-3,4,5,4'-tetramethoxystilbene, a potential anticancer drug, regulates constitutive androstane receptor (Car) target genes, but does not possess proliferative activity in mouse liver. *Toxicol Lett* [Internet]. 2019;313(March):1–10. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2019.05.024>
56. Qing Y, Debbie D, Laurence S. Characterization of mouse small intestinal cytochrome P450 expression. *Drug Metabolism and Disposition* November 2003, 31(11)1346-1351; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1124/dmd.31.11.1346>
57. Hecht SS. Inhibition of carcinogenesis by isothiocyanates. *Drug Metab Rev*. 2000;32(3–4):395–411.
58. Fahey JW, Haristoy X, Dolan PM, Kensler TW, Scholtus I, Stephenson KK, et al. and antibiotic-resistant strains of *Helicobacter pylori* and prevents benzo [a] pyrene- induced stomach tumors. *Pnas*. 2002;7610–5.
59. Anilakumar K, Farhath K, Amarinder. Dietary role of glucosinolate derivatives: a review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology-Mysore* 43.1 (2006):8-17.
60. Nori W, Roomi AB, Akram W. Platelet indices as predictors of fetal growth restriction in Pre-eclamptic Women. *Revista Latinoamericana de Hipertensión*. 2020;15(4):280-5.
61. Vargas MÁ, Rosas ME. Impacto de un programa de actividad física aeróbica en adultos mayores con hipertensión arterial. *Revista Latinoamericana de hipertensión*. 2019;14(2):142-9.
62. Gualaquiza González R, Pérez Granja A, Tapia Caisaguano A, Legña Tibanta D, Bastidas Jiménez E, Gaibor Ortiz A, Bastidas Haro T, Allauca Yumiseba M, Bravo Bohórquez G, Miranda Buenaño F, Castañeda Morales D. Incidencia y características clínicas de lactantes menores con neumonía adquirida en la comunidad ingresados en el Hospital Pediátrico “Baca Ortiz”, Ecuador. *Archivos venezolanos de farmacología y terapéutica*. 2020;39(4):260-3.